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ISLAMIC FINANCE IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBAL TRANSFORMATIONS: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article analyzes the development of Islamic finance in Uzbekistan, with particular attention to its impact on the national economy. Islamic finance, rooted in Sharia principles, is a vital and rapidly expanding segment of the global financial market, gaining traction in many countries, including Uzbekistan. The article examines global trends in Islamic finance such as the role of sukuk, Islamic banks, and emerging technologies like FinTech and their influence on economic stability and the growth of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Special attention is paid to Uzbekistan's legislative efforts aimed at building a sustainable and transparent financial system in line with Islamic standards. The paper also explores how Islamic financial instruments are used to attract investment into infrastructure projects and highlights the contribution of international organizations, such as the International Islamic Trade Finance Corporation (ITFC), in supporting socially oriented and sustainable initiatives in the country. Overall, Islamic financial tools significantly impact the Uzbek economy by enhancing the diversification and resilience of the financial system, thereby serving as a key driver of economic growth and financial inclusion.

Key words: Islamic finance, Islamic banking, Islamic bonds, sukuk, Islamic insurance, takaful, murabaha, mudaraba, ijara.

INTRODUCTION

Islamic finance represents a rapidly growing segment of the global financial market. It is grounded in the principles of Sharia law, which prohibit *riba* (usury), *maysir* (gambling), and *gharar* (excessive uncertainty), while emphasizing justice, partnership, and social responsibility. Originating in the 7th century, the Islamic financial system has undergone a long process of evolution and now operates in more than 80 countries, encompassing both Muslim and non-Muslim states. According to the Islamic Financial Services Board (IFSB), by 2023, the total value of Islamic finance assets exceeded \$3 trillion, with a projected annual growth rate of 8–10%, continuing into 2024.

In the context of the global economic shift toward more equitable, ethical, and sustainable financing models, Islamic finance is gaining increasing relevance. Uzbekistan, with its strategic location in Central Asia and rich Islamic cultural and historical heritage, is actively engaging in this process. Since 2018, the country has been taking institutional steps to establish a regulatory framework and financial infrastructure compatible with Islamic principles.

The relevance of this study is determined by the growing perception of Islamic finance in Uzbekistan not only as a religiously motivated alternative to conventional finance but also as a strategic tool for attracting investments, particularly from the Gulf States, Southeast Asia, and the Middle East. Amid rising global interest in sustainable and socially responsible finance, Islamic financial instruments (such as sukuk, *ijarah*, *mudarabah*, and *musharakah*) demonstrate high potential for financing infrastructure projects, supporting small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), and enhancing financial inclusion.

The integration of Islamic principles into national strategic documents is especially noteworthy. Under the "Uzbekistan 2030" Strategy, a concrete objective has been set: to introduce Islamic finance standards and instruments in at least three commercial banks, along with developing the legal and institutional foundations for Islamic banking and the issuance of sovereign sukuk. In 2024, significant progress was made in this direction, including the signing of memoranda with the Islamic Development Bank (IsDB) and the launch of pilot Islamic microfinance projects.

Given the global trend toward sustainable and green finance, Islamic finance can play a synergistic role in the development of Uzbekistan's national financial system contributing to diversification, fostering trust, and mobilizing both domestic and foreign investment resources. Furthermore, its alignment with ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) principles makes the sector particularly promising for financing projects in education, healthcare, agriculture, and green infrastructure.

Thus, Islamic finance is emerging not only as a religious and ethical financial tool but also as a pragmatic driver of long-term, sustainable economic growth in Uzbekistan. This study analyzes global and regional trends in Islamic finance, assesses its current status and growth potential in Uzbekistan, and offers practical recommendations for institutionalizing and scaling the sector in the medium term.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The development of the Islamic financial system in recent decades has attracted significant attention from both the academic community and practitioners. Research in this field covers a wide range of issues, from the theoretical foundations of Islamic economics to the practical mechanisms of Islamic banking operations, sukuk issuance, and the application of Islamic financial instruments in various countries.

The theoretical basis of Islamic finance is grounded in the works of authors such as M. Umer Chapra, Tariqullah Khan, Mahmoud El-Gamal, Muhammad Ayub, and others, who explore the fundamental differences between the Islamic model and traditional finance, particularly in the context of the prohibition of *riba* (usury), speculation (*mayseer*), and uncertainty (*gharar*). Their works emphasize the importance of ethical principles, fair profit and loss distribution, and the social aspect of investing.

In the context of the global trend towards sustainable and "green" financing, an increasing number of publications (e.g., Dusuki & Abozaid, 2020; IFSB Reports, 2022) emphasize the compatibility of Islamic finance with ESG principles (Environmental, Social, and Governance) and their potential in achieving the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Regarding the regional context, in the CIS countries, including Uzbekistan, Islamic finance is just beginning to form as an institutional sector. Studies by local and Middle Eastern authors (Mirzaev, 2021; Al-Suwailem, 2019) highlight the need to adapt international Islamic standards (AAOIFI, IFSB) to national conditions, establish a legal framework, and train professionals.

In Uzbekistan, the systematic consideration of Islamic banking began in 2018; however, the academic literature on the topic remains limited, particularly in terms of a comprehensive analysis of the synergy between Islamic finance and sustainable development. Existing publications mainly focus on legal aspects and regulatory frameworks, while the economic efficiency, institutional environment, and mechanisms for implementing Islamic financial instruments in banking practice require a deeper analysis.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodological foundation of this study is grounded in a comprehensive approach that integrates elements of comparative analysis, systems theory, economic and legal analysis, and the structural-functional method. This multifaceted approach facilitates a thorough examination of the development of Islamic finance both at the global level and within the specific context of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In recent decades, efforts have been made to explain the principles of Islamic finance and economics in contemporary analytical terms. However, despite a significant body of research, there remains confusion regarding the precise definitions of terms such as "Islamic economy" and "Islamic finance." This confusion often arises due to an isolated approach to various aspects of the system, making it difficult to understand its holistic nature.

For example, "Islamic finance" is often associated with the prohibition of "interest," which is an oversimplified and inaccurate definition. An additional complication is the lack of knowledge among some researchers about Islam, its foundations, history, and the Arabic language, which is further exacerbated by the politicized environment in which these issues are discussed. [2]

Picture 1. Islamic financial instruments¹.

Picture 1 illustrates the widely recognized Islamic financial sectors and instruments that strictly adhere to the core principles of Shariah. These principles prohibit *riba* (interest), *maysir* (speculation), and involvement in haram activities, thereby excluding any financial transactions involving interest, excessive uncertainty, or gambling, as well as the financing of companies engaged in prohibited activities such as the production of alcohol, weapons, or gambling operations.

Shariah principles are implemented through a two-tiered Shariah screening methodology aimed at assessing asset compliance with Islamic legal norms. The qualitative screening ensures the exclusion of companies engaged in prohibited activities, including the production and sale of pork, alcohol, tobacco, and gambling, as well as the provision of conventional financial services based on interest and derivatives. The quantitative screening focuses on financial metrics, establishing threshold values for leverage, liquidity, and revenue derived from prohibited activities. These principles ensure that only assets meeting rigorous standards are included in investment portfolios, thereby mitigating risks and enhancing financial stability. [3]

Islamic finance plays a crucial role in the global economy by contributing to the diversification of financial markets and the reduction of systemic risks. Islamic financial models, which prioritize risk-sharing over interest-based transactions, enhance financial stability. Empirical analysis conducted in 2023 confirms that lending within the Islamic banking sector in the post-COVID-19 period exhibits counter-cyclical behavior, making it an effective hedging instrument in economies with an Islamic banking system. Empirical data, including weekly economic activity indicators, indicate a significant increase in lending to small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Turkey despite the economic crisis. Unlike traditional deposit banks, Islamic banks, which operate with a lower asset ratio, demonstrate higher lending activity, underscoring their role in stabilizing the economy during periods of economic shocks. The proactive and aggressive lending policies implemented in response to the pandemic enabled Islamic banks to effectively support SMEs, reducing bankruptcy rates and mitigating the adverse effects of the crisis. These findings reveal significant differences between Islamic and conventional deposit-based lending in crisis situations and highlight the pivotal role of Islamic banks in sustaining SME resilience amid economic disruptions. [4]

Furthermore, Islamic finance contributes to economic resilience by fostering financial markets that support not only commercial but also social objectives. For instance, empirical research indicates that integrated Islamic social finance is 12% more effective in improving the living conditions of the poor compared to programs that do not adopt an integrated approach. This study underscores the importance of implementing integrated Islamic social finance to accelerate the well-being of low-income populations. [5]

An essential aspect is the development of Islamic financial technologies (FinTech). In recent years, Islamic financial models have been actively integrating with emerging technologies, including blockchain and cryptocurrencies, significantly enhancing the accessibility of financial services, particularly in developing countries. Research identifies opportunities for integrating FinTech solutions into Islamic financial systems to support non-banking institutions and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). The adoption of FinTech

¹ Developed by the author based on the studied materials

in Islamic finance also improves financial inclusion, helps overcome economic crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic, and contributes to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals, fostering the creation of a stable and resilient economy. [6]

In 2023, the assets of the global Islamic financial services industry (IFSI) grew by 4% compared to the previous year, reaching USD 3.38 trillion despite a challenging macroeconomic environment characterized by inflationary pressures, geopolitical tensions, and issues within the banking sector. Islamic banking remains the largest segment of the IFSI, accounting for 70.21% of the sector's total assets in 2023, while issued sukuk and Islamic funds collectively represent 29.08%, and the Islamic insurance (Takaful) segment accounts for 0.71%. In terms of regional distribution, the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) region holds the largest share of global Islamic financial sector assets, comprising more than 52.50%, followed by East Asia and the Pacific region with 21.80%. The Middle East and North Africa (excluding GCC countries) account for 12.70%, Europe and Central Asia for 8.30%, South Asia for 3.10%, Sub-Saharan Africa for 0.70%, while other regions collectively make up 0.90%. [7]

According to the data presented in Table 1, the total resources of the Islamic financial industry are determined as the sum of all its segments. From 2021–2023, a steady increase in this total has been observed, rising from USD 3,058.7 billion in 2021 to USD 3,378.51 billion in 2023. This trend indicates positive growth and the expanding scale of the global Islamic financial industry. Despite a decline in the volume of Islamic fund assets and fluctuations in Takaful contributions, the overall trend reflects the continued development of the Islamic financial system. This growth is largely driven by the expansion of Islamic banking and the issuance of sukuk, highlighting the strong interest in these financial instruments and their increasing role in the global financial landscape.

Table 1. Distribution of the Global Islamic Financial Industry by Sector (USD billion).

	2021	2022	2023
Islamic Banking Assets	2 104,1	2 249,2	2 372,17
Sukuk Outstanding	775,7	829,7	850,0
Islamic Funds Assets	154,6	136,6	132,29
Takaful Contributions	24,3	30,0	24,05
Total	3 058,7	3 245,5	3 378,51

Uzbekistan is actively developing its legal and regulatory framework for Islamic financial operations. In recent years, significant progress has been made in establishing regulatory acts aimed at forming a stable and transparent financial system that aligns with Islamic principles. One key legislative development has been the adoption of the Law “On Non-Banking Credit Organizations and Microfinance”, which introduces new regulations for the operations of microfinance institutions, pawnshops, and mortgage refinancing organizations. Under this law, microfinance institutions are authorized to provide loans, leasing, factoring, and Islamic financial services in compliance with Shariah standards, as established by the Central Bank of Uzbekistan. [8]

Additionally, the Resolution of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Approval of Regulations for the Provision of Islamic Financial Services by Microfinance Organizations” governs the procedures for offering Islamic financial services by microfinance institutions. This legislation also regulates the activities of non-banking credit organizations, prohibiting them from engaging in production, insurance, trade, or deposit collection, while placing them under the supervision of the Central Bank of Uzbekistan. The implementation of this law is expected to significantly advance the Islamic finance market in the country, enhance financial stability, and attract new investments. [9]

The use of sukuk for financing infrastructure projects in Uzbekistan could significantly enhance access to capital investments. The country faces considerable infrastructure modernization needs, and Islamic financial instruments can serve as an effective means of attracting the required capital. A notable example of financial cooperation is the agreement for Murabaha financing worth \$300 million between the International Islamic Trade Finance Corporation (ITFC) and Uzbekistan. This financing aims to ensure food security and agricultural resilience by securing stable wheat supplies. Since commencing operations in Central Asia, ITFC has allocated \$2 billion, with \$1.38 billion designated for supporting the private sector and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Specifically, Uzbekistan has received \$530 million, Kazakhstan \$810 million, Turkmenistan \$25 million, and Kyrgyzstan \$23 million.

The primary focus of these financial measures is to support women-led SMEs and promote “green” financing principles, thereby expanding the role of SMEs in regional economic development. Under the cooperation agreement between Uzbekistan and ITFC for 2024–2026, financing opportunities for SMEs are expected to

expand further. ITFC continues to strengthen its presence in the region, particularly in Uzbekistan, where it remains committed to providing financial services aimed at sustainable development and supporting local SMEs across various economic sectors (Islamic Trade Finance Corporation, 2024). [10]

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The development of Islamic finance in Uzbekistan is accompanied by various institutional, legal, and organizational challenges, requiring a comprehensive and phased approach to overcome them. Below are the key issues hindering the broader adoption of Islamic financial instruments in the national economy, along with proposed solutions. The lack of systematic training programs for specialists in Islamic banking, jurisprudence, and financial engineering limits the industry's growth. To address this issue, universities in Uzbekistan should introduce specialized educational programs, preferably in collaboration with international institutions such as the Islamic Development Bank (IsDB) and the Islamic Corporation for the Development of the Private Sector (ICD).

Additionally, capacity-building programs should be intensified, and international internships and experience-sharing initiatives with leading Islamic finance hubs such as Malaysia, Bahrain, and the UAE should be organized. Many entrepreneurs, particularly those in the small and medium-sized enterprise (SME) sector, have limited knowledge about Islamic financial opportunities.

A potential solution is to conduct large-scale informational and educational campaigns, create online platforms that explain Islamic financial products in an accessible manner, and showcase successful case studies demonstrating the practical application of Islamic finance. Currently, only basic forms of Islamic financing, such as Ijarah and Mudarabah, are in use. To expand the product lineup, new instruments such as Takaful (Islamic insurance), Islamic ETFs, and crowdfunding platforms should be introduced. These initiatives should ideally be launched as pilot programs with the support of international organizations and donors. A structural challenge is the lack of a liquid market for trading Islamic securities, particularly sukuk. A viable solution would be to establish a dedicated Islamic finance section on the Tashkent Stock Exchange and issue the country's first sovereign sukuk. Another crucial step is the development of market-making institutions to ensure liquidity. Collectively, these measures will enable Uzbekistan to establish a competitive Islamic financial system and integrate it into the global financial landscape, strengthening economic resilience and attracting investment inflows.

The development of Islamic finance in Uzbekistan requires a phased, institutionally sound approach based on international best practices and the country's socio-economic realities. Addressing existing barriers and implementing effective solutions will facilitate the creation of a robust Islamic financial sector capable of contributing to sustainable growth, financial inclusion, and the expansion of the country's investment potential.

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